

1 **Genes that function in aging in humans.**

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1. Sirtuins
 2. Growth differentiation factors
 - 7 a. GDF15
 - 8 3. Insulin-like growth factors
 - 8 a. Igf1 and Igf1R
 - 9 4. Mboat family
 - 9 a. Mboat7
 - 10 5. MyoD and other myogenic factors
 - 10 6. Hemopexin, Pejuvkin and Hepsin
 - 11 7. Interferon-stimulated genes (ISGs)
 - 11 a. IFITM family
 - 12 8. Iron transport and metabolism
 - 12 a. Tfr
 - 13 b. Ferroportin
 - 13 c. Hpcidin
 - 14 9. Tox
 - 14 10. Other LOCs and ncRNAs
 - 15 11. Positions of interest